

University of Novi Sad | Faculty of Sciences
DEPARTMENT OF GEOGRAPHY, TOURISM AND HOTEL MANAGEMENT

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

STRENGTH 2024

**STRENGTHENING SUSTAINABILITY COMMUNICATION IN TOURISM,
HOSPITALITY, AND EVENT INDUSTRIES**

August 22nd, 2024

Book of Abstracts

The publication is part of the activities of the project: „Strengthening digital sustainability communication in tourism and culture between US and Serbia “. This project was supported by the U.S. Embassy Belgrade. The opinions and conclusions expressed herein are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the U.S. Government.

Novi Sad, August 2024

Book of Abstracts

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE - STRENGTH 2024

STRENGTHENING SUSTAINABILITY COMMUNICATION IN TOURISM, HOSPITALITY, AND
EVEN INDUSTRIES

Publisher: University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geography, Tourism and
Hotel Management

Editor in Chief

Dr. Milica Pavkov Hrvojević, Dean

Editorial Board

Prof. Lazar Lazić

Prof. Tatjana Pivac

Prof. Igor Stamenković

Prof. Sanja Kovačić

Prof. Đorđije Vasiljević

Prof. Miroslav Vujičić

Prof. Bojana Kalenjuk Pivarski

Contents

International Scientific Board	4
Sustainable Tourism Through Extended Reality: Lessons from Heritage Destinations in Serbia	5
Enhancing Sustainability Communication Through the Beverage Lens	6
Addressing Artificial Intelligence Bias in Accessible Smart Tourism for Sustainable Development ...	7
The Impact of Film as a Segment of Creative and Cultural Industries on Intangible Heritage and Tourism	9
Strengthening Digital Sustainability Communication in Tourism and Culture Between US and Serbia Through International Cooperation	10
The Digital Carbon Footprint of the Tourism, Hospitality, and Events Industries.....	11
Micro-Green Framework: Conceptualizing Green Skills Development Through Microlearning in the Workplace	13
Use of ICT in Museum Interpretation - Lessons from Serbia.....	15

International Scientific Board

- Lazar Lazić, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geography, Tourism and Hotel Management, Novi Sad, Serbia
- Brooke K. Hansen, University of South Florida, MUMA College of Business School of Hospitality and Tourism Management, Tampa, USA
- James Kennell, Department of Marketing, Events and Tourism, Faculty of Business, University of Greenwich, UK
- Laura K. Harrison, University of South Florida, USA Access 3D Lab,
- Miroslav D. Vujičić, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geography, Tourism and Hotel Management, Novi Sad, Serbia
- Adam B. Carmer, University of South Florida, MUMA College of Business School of Hospitality and Tourism Management, Tampa, USA
- Ugljesa Stankov, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geography, Tourism and Hotel Management, Novi Sad, Serbia
- Marija Bratić, Faculty of Sciences, University of Niš, Serbia
- Dino Mujkić, Faculty of Sport and Physical Education, University of Sarajevo, Sarajevo Meeting of Culture (NGO), BiH
- Sebastian Kaiser-Jovy, Heilbronn University, Germany
- Jelena Farkić, Breda University of Applied Sciences, Breda, Netherlands
- Iva Slivar, Juraj Dobrila University of Pula, Faculty of Economics and Tourism, Croatia
- Aleksa Vučetić, Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality, University of Montenegro, Kotor, Montenegro
- Danijel Pavlović, Academy of Hospitality, Tourism and Wellness, Belgrade, Serbia
- Lazar Pavić, University of Maribor, Faculty of Logistics, Slovenia
- Cezar Morar, University, Department of Geography, Tourism & Territorial Planning, FGTS, University of Oradea

The Digital Carbon Footprint of the Tourism, Hospitality, and Events Industries

Stankov, U., Filimonau, S. Kennell, J., Vujičić, M.D.

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geography, Tourism and Hotel Management, Serbia; University of Surrey, School of Tourism and Hospitality Management, United Kingdom

ugljesa.stankov@dgt.uns.ac.rs

Abstract: The digital carbon footprint refers to the greenhouse gas emissions resulting from the use of digital technologies, such as electronic devices, web servers and data centers, and treatment of electronic waste. The digital carbon footprint of the tourism, hospitality, and events industries (THE) is increasingly significant due to the proliferation of technology-driven tourism services and evolving consumption trends. Despite the necessity to understand the implications of this for green transitions and the industries themselves, scholarly investigations into THE's digital carbon footprint are limited. This paper outlines a provisional research agenda for analyzing THE's digital carbon footprint. To support its arguments, this paper draws on academic and grey literature on the emerging topic of the digital carbon footprint. The proposed research agenda considers four perspectives representing different actors in THE's value chain: suppliers, industry professionals, consumers, and policymakers. Additionally, it explores the broader societal spillover effects of THE's digital carbon footprint. This paper delineates research directions aimed at assisting various actors within THE's value chain and academics in comprehending the phenomenon of the digital carbon footprint.

Keywords: Digital Footprint; Carbon Dioxide Emissions; The Industries; Green Transition.

Acknowledgement: This paper is based upon work from COST Action CA19142—Leading Platform for European Citizens, Industries, Academia and Policymakers in Media Accessibility (LEAD-ME) supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology); HORIZON TMA MSCA Staff Exchanges: ClearClimate (grant agreement No 101131220); and H2020-LC-GD-2020-3 GreenScenT-Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future (grant agreement No 101036480) that have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. This paper was also supported by the U.S. Embassy in Belgrade (grant number SRB10023GR0052).

CIP - Каталогизacija y publikaciji
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

338.484:502.131.1(048.3)

INTERNATIONAL scientific conference Strenght 2024 Strenghtening sustainability communication in tourism, hospitality, and event industries 2024 ; Novi Sad

Book of abstracts [Elektronski izvor] / International scientific conference Strenght 2024 Strenghtening sustainability communication in tourism, hospitality, and even industries, August 22nd, 2024, Novi Sad ; [organised by] University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geography, Tourism and Hotel Management ; [editor in chief Milica Pavkov Hrvojević]. - Novi Sad : Faculty of Sciences, Department of Geography, Tourism and Hotel Management, 2024. - 1 elektronski optički disk (CD-ROM) : tekst ; 24 cm

Način pristupa (URL): <http://www.dgt.uns.ac.rs/strenght-2024/>. - Nasl. sa naslovnog ekrana. - Sistemski zahtevi: Nisu navedeni.

ISBN 978-86-7031-659-1

а) Туризам -- Одрживи развој -- Апстрактн

COBISS.SR-ID 150848265